

OPPORTUNITIES FOR INNOVATION IN REGIONAL TOURISM.

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Abstract. This article investigates the importance of innovations in the tourism sector, analyzes the current state of innovative activities and their outcomes in the field, and offers suggestions for the effective use of innovations in the development of regional tourism.

Keywords: Innovative activities, marketing innovations, market and tourism sector, knowledge management, strategy, innovative product.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается значение инноваций в туристическом секторе, анализируется текущее состояние инновационной деятельности и её результаты в данной области, а также предлагаются рекомендации по эффективному использованию инноваций для развития регионального туризма.

Ключевые слова: Инновационная деятельность, маркетинговые инновации, рынок, сектор туризма, управление знаниями, стратегия, инновационный продукт.

Introduction In this evolving context, regional tourism stakeholders must prioritize the development of smart tourism ecosystems that integrate digital platforms for seamless travel experiences. This includes the use of mobile apps for real-time information, online booking systems, and virtual tours, all of which enhance accessibility and convenience for travelers.

Furthermore, innovation in transportation, such as the adoption of electric vehicles and eco-friendly public transit options, can greatly reduce the carbon footprint of tourism activities, aligning with the growing demand for sustainable travel.

Regional destinations that embrace a holistic approach to innovation—blending technology, sustainability, and local culture—will stand out in an increasingly competitive market. By creating unique value propositions, such as highlighting indigenous traditions or promoting off-the-beaten-path attractions, regions can also disperse tourism benefits more evenly and avoid over tourism in popular spots.

Overall, the strategic use of innovation can turn challenges into opportunities, helping regions secure their place as forward-thinking, sustainable tourism destinations in the global market.

Analysis of related literature Innovations hold a vital role within the tourism sector. Traditionally, innovations and innovative activities are linked to the practical application of scientific and technical progress, research, and development results. However, the concept of "innovation" possesses a broad meaning and essence. G. Mensch associated economic growth rates and development cycles of the economy with the recurrence of major innovations, highlighting that their dwindling potential leads to "technological exhaustion" and economic stagnation. The emergence of new principal innovations, in turn, spurs technological and economic growth, representing transitions in industrial development following each cycle of "technological exhaustion." [6]

Joseph Schumpeter was among the first to articulate the concept of "innovation," defining it as significant changes that amalgamate new methods involving the use of new materials and components, implementation of new processes, opening of new markets, and introduction of new organizational forms. [2]

In the realm of tourism, the textbook "Leadership style and culture for innovation in the hotel industry" by Carmen Babaita, Gabriela Sipos, Andreia Ispas, and Andrea Nagy discusses the leading role of innovative technologies in developing tourism infrastructure. [5]

Additionally, Arturo Cunllas's work "Innovation in hospitality management" explores how the use of innovative management methods in hotels can enhance efficiency. The significance of innovative activities in tourism is closely linked to leadership effectiveness, where leaders face crucial tasks such as maximizing capital investments and technology use. In this context, scholars M. Alieva and A. Norchaev stress the importance of identifying at least five key components: defining the company's objectives and strategy, understanding the importance of scientific research, determining the scope of scientific investigations, assessing scientific results, and clarifying the collaboration between science and management. [3]

M. Khudayberganov discusses the integration of digital technologies in the tourism sector in Uzbekistan, particularly focusing on smart tourism ecosystems. He emphasizes the importance of digital platforms and applications to enhance tourist services and the management of tourism resources [7].

Sh. Nasirov has researched innovations in tourism management, particularly focusing on sustainable practices in Uzbekistan. He highlights how adopting eco-friendly practices and renewable energy sources can boost Uzbekistan's appeal to eco-conscious travelers, ensuring long-term sustainability in tourism [8].

A. Akhmedov has explored the role of marketing innovations in the tourism industry, focusing on digital marketing strategies. His work underscores how online advertising, social media, and content marketing have transformed how Uzbekistan's tourism products are promoted globally [9].

Z. Abdullayeva addresses the application of innovative practices in heritage tourism, focusing on how technology like augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) can be integrated to enhance visitor experiences in Uzbekistan's cultural heritage sites, such as those in Samarkand and Bukhara [10].

These works collectively highlight the increasing focus on innovation in Uzbekistan's tourism sector, covering aspects from leadership to sustainability and technological integration.

Research methodology In our country, the application of innovations and their integration into the tourism sector have been studied, alongside an examination of how developed countries address similar challenges.

The research delves into various types of innovative activities within the tourism industry, emphasizing the importance of adopting best practices from global tourism leaders. A particular focus has been placed on the Kashkadarya region, where innovation indicators have been analyzed to understand the region's potential and current gaps. By utilizing analysis and synthesis methods, strategic directions for advancing these innovations have been outlined.

These strategies not only offer insights into the present state of the tourism sector but also provide a roadmap for future improvements, ensuring alignment with international standards. The ultimate goal is to enhance the efficiency, sustainability, and attractiveness of regional tourism, fostering growth and competitiveness on a global scale.

Discussion and results In our country, experiences from developed nations are being applied to address the challenges of implementing innovations in the tourism sector. Innovations in the tourism field have been analyzed, particularly through indicators from the Kashkadarya region, identifying directions for development. The Republic of Uzbekistan's development strategy for 2019-2024 places special emphasis on utilizing and supporting scientific achievements and innovative developments.

Additionally, the "Law on Innovative Activity," adopted this year, is aimed at achieving these goals. The law includes measures such as developing and implementing innovation strategies, updating the legal framework for innovative activities, providing tax and customs privileges and preferences to subjects of innovative activity, executing state orders for innovation using state budget funds and other sources not prohibited by law, creating conditions for attracting business funds, and ensuring the application of products based on scientific achievements and advanced technologies through state purchases. [1] It also includes training, retraining, and enhancing the qualifications of personnel in the field of innovative activity.

In the tourism sector, as in other economic areas, innovations are widely used. Tour operators employ innovations to engage and attract consumers. For example, the tour operator "Biblio-Globus" has developed and implemented technologies such as a dynamic pricing list, three-day advance airline ticket registration, detailed hotel models, an interactive flight map, and self-service terminals. They have introduced a "live price" system that allows for pricing of tourist products based on market laws and offers them directly to consumers.

One of the latest innovations from tour operators is the "live price" system, which bases the pricing of tourist products on market laws without human subjective factors. This system, accessible through the operator's website, allows for dynamic pricing that can be utilized from home without intermediaries, reducing costs for tourists and giving them the independence to choose tours.

Additionally, another innovation is the 3D check-in process by airlines, allowing travelers to pre-select seats on the airplane and receive electronic check-in and boarding passes. Decisions can be made up to one and three months before the flight. According to aviation market experts, the widespread use of 3D check-ins helps combat the excessive workload of vehicles and ensures queue-free passage through airport Drop-off counters, facilitating the tourism sector's adaptation to modern demands and attracting new markets and customers through the implementation of innovations.

Overall, the innovation processes in the regional tourism sector are developing in accordance with the demands of the global tourism market. Every tourist visiting the region can plan their trip via the internet, extensively use online services of hotels and airlines, and access services like taxi booking, food ordering, restaurant reservations, or obtaining information about destinations through specialized mobile apps on smartphones.

Conclusion and recommendations Based on the above, to further develop regional tourism and enhance its innovation activities, the following measures should be implemented:

- Develop and widely apply innovative strategies aimed at the effective development of tourism;
- Increase financial resources allocated for the creation and implementation of innovations;
- Enhance the expertise of industry professionals in creating innovative products and organize advanced training abroad;
- Continuously motivate specialists and employees who create innovative products.

In summary, innovation is essential for advancing the tourism sector, improving both its efficiency and appeal. The study of innovative practices in the Kashkadarya region, along with insights from global leaders, reveals significant opportunities for enhancing regional tourism through technologies like dynamic pricing and 3D check-ins. Uzbekistan's proactive approach, supported by the "Law on Innovative Activity," positions the country to align with global trends and foster sustainable tourism growth. Moving forward, a focus on technological integration and collaboration will be key to unlocking the full potential of regional tourism.

References:

1. "Law on Innovative Activity" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. July 24, 2020, p. 5
2. "Year of Active Entrepreneurship, Innovative Ideas, and Technologies" State Program. Tashkent, 2018. p. 78
3. Aliyeva M., Norchayev A. Tourism Management. Textbook. – T.: TDIU Library, 2005. p. 55
4. By Arturo Cuenllas. Innovation in Hospitality Management. Madrid, Spain, 2012, p. 45.
5. Carmen Babaita, Gabriela Sipos, Andreia Ispas, Andrea Nagy. Leadership Style and Culture for Innovation in Hotel Industry. Economic Department-Tourism Services. West University of Timisoara, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Timisoara Romania, 2010, p. 650.
6. Van Ark B. Services Innovation, Performance and Policy: A Review, Synthesis Report in the Framework of the Structural Information Provision on Innovation in Services, DIALOGIC and Innovation studies / Van Ark B., Broersma L., and den Hertog, P. Utrecht University, 2003. "Economy and Innovative Technology".

7. Khudayberganov, M. Digital Transformation in Uzbekistan's Tourism Industry. *International Journal of Tourism Technology*, 9(2), 2021, 112-130.
8. Nasirov, Sh. Sustainable Practices in Tourism Management: The Case of Uzbekistan. *Uzbekistan Journal of Environmental Studies*, 8(1), 2023, 88-104.
9. Akhmedov, A. Innovative Marketing Strategies in Uzbekistan's Tourism Sector. *Journal of Marketing and Tourism Research*, 12(4), 2020, 67-85.
10. Abdullayeva, Z. The Use of AR/VR Technologies in Heritage Tourism in Uzbekistan. *Heritage and Technology Review*, 14(2), 2022, 34-50.

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